

Research

The Impact of Consumer Price Index on Economic Growth in Selected ASEAN Countries

Tin Zar Zar Lynn^{1*}

¹School of Economics, Guangxi University, Nanning, 530004, China

Abstract: The main purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of the consumer price index (CPI) on economic growth for three selected ASEAN countries, Myanmar, Singapore, and Thailand, using annual time series data for the period 1990–2021. The data necessary for this study were obtained from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank Statistical Organizations. Descriptive statistics and exponential growth curve analysis are commonly employed in order to assess and contrast the levels of volatility exhibited by the consumer price index and economic growth. Based on the findings of descriptive statistics, it can be observed that Singapore shows a higher degree of stability in both its consumer price index and economic growth when compared to Thailand and Myanmar. In contrast to Myanmar, Thailand has a higher degree of consistency in its consumer price index and economic development. Myanmar exhibits the highest degree of unpredictability in the consumer price index and economic growth. The findings of this study indicate that economic growth in the three selected nations was influenced by the consumer price index, as predicted by the projected exponential growth curve model.

Keywords: Consumer Price Index (CPI), GDP per capita (current year US \$)), exponential growth curve model, ASEAN

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 30 December, 2023; **Published:** 3 January, 2024

How to cite this article: Tin Zar Zar Lynn (2023). *The Impact of Consumer Price Index on Economic Growth in Selected ASEAN Countries*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(12), 49-67. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10452176>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

One of the most popular metrics is the gross domestic product (GDP) when gauging economic performance. Gross domestic product (GDP) is a metric used to quantify the overall economic production of a nation within a specific time frame. It is subjected to seasonal adjustments to mitigate the influence of quarterly fluctuations that may arise due to climatic conditions or holiday-related factors. The GDP metric that garners the highest level of scrutiny is also subjected to inflation adjustments to assess variations in output rather than fluctuations in the pricing of goods and services. The comparison of country economies by size is often facilitated by utilising annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) figures. Business executives, financial market participants, and politicians exhibit heightened interest in fluctuations in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) over a given period, typically expressed as an annualised rate of expansion or contraction. This facilitates the comparison of annual and quarterly rates.

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is an essential indicator for economists and investors due to its ability to quantify fluctuations in the magnitude of the aggregate economy. Gross domestic product (GDP) figures offer a comprehensive evaluation of the economy and shed light on the factors that contribute to or hinder economic growth.

A significant correlation exists between economic growth and share prices, as heightened economic growth often leads to improved firm profitability and increased investor risk tolerance. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that robust GDP growth has the potential to impact fixed-income assets such as bonds negatively. This is mostly because increased GDP growth can lead to reduced bond returns, diminishing their relative attractiveness compared to other investment options.

The consumer price index (CPI) is a tool for quantifying inflation. This method is employed to assess the mean fluctuation between two specified time intervals in the costs of goods and services consumed by households. The Consumer Price Index (CPI) is a metric utilised to gauge price fluctuations for goods and services acquired by families in their capacity as consumers. The metric is commonly employed as a surrogate indicator of overall economic inflation, mostly because of its frequent and timely generation. The hand mentioned above has seen significant development and now holds substantial importance in the process of crafting economic policies, namely in the realm of monetary policy. The metric in question is commonly recognised as the appropriate measure for including the effects of inflation on various payments, including salaries, rentals, interest, social security, benefits, and pensions, within legal frameworks and diverse contractual agreements. According to the International Monetary Fund's Consumer Price Index Manual: Concepts and Methods (2020), this situation's consequences might have substantial and extensive financial implications for individuals and businesses.

The Consumer Price Index (CPI) is widely employed as a fundamental instrument for quantifying the levels of inflation and deflation. Inflation is a significant metric for assessing the overall well-being of an economy. Governments and central banks rely on the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and other similar indices to inform their economic decision-making processes. A significantly fluctuating inflation rate possesses the capacity to inflict substantial economic damage. Nominal contracts are associated with an increased level of risk premia and unexpected alterations in the distribution of wealth due to the presence of uncertainty regarding future pricing. As mentioned earlier, the costs indicate that increased inflation volatility might have a detrimental effect on economic growth, assuming a specific average inflation rate (Elder, 2004; Fatás and Mihov, 2005; Grier and Grier, 2006). Extensive economic theory and econometric analysis have been dedicated to examining the effects of monetary policy on the volatility of inflation. Notable contributions in this area include the works of Gali and Monacelli (2005) and Leduc and Sill (2007).

One of the primary considerations revolves around the decision to increase or decrease interest rates. An increase in interest rates leads to an escalation in the cost of borrowing funds. Reducing interest rates has a counteractive impact and was originally designed to stimulate consumer expenditure to maintain inflation levels within a nation's targeted range. The GDP price index, similar to the CPI, quantifies the fluctuations in prices of consumer products and services. However, it also encompasses the price variations of goods and services acquired by enterprises, governments, and individuals from other countries.

In contrast to the Consumer Price Index (CPI), the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) price index does not assess price fluctuations specifically for imported goods. Gross domestic product (GDP) is a metric used to quantify the total value of goods and services generated inside a country's borders over a specific time, often one year. The indicator is often regarded as a pivotal gauge of a country's economic well-being, and a favorable change indicates economic advancement.

The ASEAN region in Asia includes the countries of Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. In 2021, Singapore exhibited a gross domestic product (GDP) per capita of approximately 72,794 U.S. dollars, while Thailand and Myanmar recorded figures of roughly 7,336 and 1,216 dollars, respectively.

According to data from 2019, it was observed that the gross domestic product (GDP) in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) countries amounted to 3.0 trillion U.S. dollars at current prices. This figure represents approximately 3.5% of the global GDP. Additionally, the GDP per capita in these countries was recorded at 4601 US dollars. The gross domestic product (GDP) growth rate, measured in constant prices, is 5.2 per cent. The projected gross domestic product (GDP) of all member nations in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) for 2021 and beyond, amounting to around 3.35 trillion U.S. dollars, represents significant growth compared to previous estimations. The GDP of the ASEAN region has experienced an important upward trajectory, indicative of the robust economic development within the region.

In 2021, Singapore emerged as the ASEAN member with the highest human development index (HDI) score, recording a score of 0.939. This was closely trailed by Thailand, which obtained a score of 0.800, and Myanmar, which achieved a score of 0.585. This study involves a comparative analysis as it examines the Human Development Index (HDI) of Myanmar, Singapore, and Thailand. Myanmar is categorized as having a low HDI, while Singapore and Thailand are recognized for having the highest HDIs.

Price stability is a prerequisite for attaining sustainable economic growth in nations. Price stability refers to a state in which the overall price level in the economy remains relatively constant without experiencing substantial swings that result in major increases or decreases in the Consumer Price Index (CPI). Price stability has a significant role in facilitating elevated levels of economic activity and employment through several means. In contemporary times, a correlation exists between the consumer price index and economic growth. The research problem addressed in this article pertains to the relationship between the consumer price index and economic development, positing a beneficial impact.

The objectives of the study are:

- (i) To investigate the relationship between economic growth and consumer price index.
- (ii) To analyze the impact of consumer price index on economic growth of selected ASEAN countries.

Literature review

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is an economic indicator that holds significant importance due to its widely recognized status as the primary metric for assessing the well-being of individuals within a given society. The fundamental concept is that GDP simultaneously quantifies two aspects: the aggregate revenue generated within an economy by all participants and the total expenditure made by the government to acquire goods and services inside the economy (Todaro, 2010).

Indonesia employs the consumer price index to assess the expenditure allocated towards development initiatives. The individual aims to give financial resources towards various development programmes, stimulate economic expansion (as quantified by increasing GDP figures), and provide job opportunities, which can potentially mitigate poverty. Halim (2016) states that certain loans require principal and interest payments.

According to a study by Junaedi (2020), the findings indicate a significant correlation between the consumer price index and the state of the national economy, particularly the Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Fischer and Modigliani (1978) posited a theoretical framework that suggests a non-linear and negative relationship between inflation rates and economic development, drawing upon mechanisms derived from the new growth theory (Malla, 1997). It is argued that inflation primarily hinders economic progress by reducing investment efficiency instead of just lowering investment levels.

In their study, Gokal and Hanif (2004) analyzed the relationship between inflation and economic development in Fiji. This investigation involved the application of various economic theories. The study's results indicated a moderate inverse relationship between the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). According to the results of the causality test, a unidirectional relationship exists between GDP and inflation.

Mallik and Chowdhury (2001) derived two primary conclusions from their investigation. The empirical findings indicate a significant positive association between inflation and economic growth in Bangladesh, Pakistan, India, and Sri Lanka. Furthermore, it is more probable that inflation will experience greater fluctuations compared to the changes in economic growth. According to Shahzad (2011), there exists a positive and strong correlation between inflation and economic growth in Pakistan. According to the findings of Iqbal and Nawaz (2009), it was determined that maintaining an inflation rate of 6 percent or lower is optimal for fostering economic growth. Additionally, their research revealed a significant and adverse association between inflation rates exceeding 6 percent and economic growth.

The study conducted by Ahmed and Mortaza (2005) examined the relationship between the gross domestic product (GDP) and the consumer price index (CPI) of Bangladesh. The findings indicate that the economy of Bangladesh should maintain an inflation rate of no more than 6%. Based on the empirical analysis conducted, it has been observed that there exists a long-term inverse correlation between the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

2.1 Measuring GDP

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is the market value of all final goods and services created inside a country's borders within a certain time frame (quarter or year). This encompasses both goods and services that are accessible in the open market as well as non-market services provided by the government, such as defense and education. Moreover, gross national product (GNP) can be employed as an alternative to gross domestic product (GDP) to estimate the total output of a country. As an illustration, in the scenario where a German business establishes and maintains a manufacturing facility within the United States, the output generated by the firm would be accounted for in the United States Gross Domestic Product (GDP) rather than being attributed to Germany's GDP.

Not all forms of productive activity are accounted for in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) calculation. The exclusion of black market activities and unpaid labour, such as volunteer work performed at home or elsewhere, is due to the inherent difficulty in accurately assessing and quantifying their worth. If a baker produces a loaf of bread for a customer, it would contribute to the gross domestic product (GDP). However, if the same baker makes the loaf for his own family, it would not be included in the GDP calculation, although the expenses incurred for purchasing the ingredients would still be accounted for. Moreover, the concept of gross domestic product fails to incorporate the depreciation of capital stock, which refers to the gradual deterioration of equipment, structures, and other assets utilized in the production process. Net domestic product (NDP) is derived by deducting the depletion of the capital stock, commonly referred to as depreciation, from the gross domestic product (GDP).

A country's gross domestic product (GDP) represents the monetary value of the final goods and services produced inside its borders over a given time frame, such as a quarter or a year. It also includes the value of goods and services consumed by the end user. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) encompasses the total value of all goods and services generated within a nation's territorial borders. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) comprises marketable goods and services produced for consumption, together with non-market outputs like defence or educational services provided by the government. The phrase "gross national product" (GNP) refers to a distinct concept encompassing a nation's production of goods and services. The calculation of GDP only includes some types of productive activities. Moreover, the idea of gross domestic product fails to incorporate the depreciation of the capital stock, which refers to the gradual deterioration and obsolescence of equipment, structures, and other assets utilized in the production process. Net domestic product (NDP) is calculated by deducting the depreciation of the capital stock from the gross domestic product (GDP).

2.2 Real GDP

People are curious to know if an economy's total output of goods and services is growing or shrinking. The calculation of GDP uses nominal or current figures, rendering it impractical to compare two temporal periods without incorporating adjustments for inflation. To obtain the "actual" Gross Domestic Product (GDP), it is necessary to adjust the nominal GDP to account for price changes. This will facilitate the determination of whether the augmented output value may be attributed to a rise in production or merely to higher prices. The price deflator is a statistical instrument that converts nominal GDP into constant prices.

The expected outcome is a rise in employment levels as companies expand their workforce in response to increased demand for their products, coupled with a boost in consumer spending resulting from a rapid growth in real GDP. Similar to many nations affected by the ongoing global economic crisis, a reduction in employment frequently coincides with a decrease in GDP. Although there may be occasional fluctuations in the GDP, its growth rate might need to be sufficiently swift to adequately meet the employment needs of individuals seeking job opportunities.

However, it is worth noting that real GDP growth exhibits cyclical patterns over time. While it is commonly accepted that two consecutive quarters of declining production indicate a recession, it is important to recognise that economies can also have periods of expansion, sluggish development, or even severe economic downturns known as depressions.

2.3 Consumer Price Index (CPI)

Consumer price indexes (CPIs) measure the degree to which the prices of products and services purchased, obtained, or utilized by households for their needs and wants have changed over time. The calculation of most consumer price indexes (CPIs) involves the use of weighted averages. These averages are derived from the percentage price rises of certain consumer goods baskets. The weights assigned to each item in the baskets reflect their relative significance in household consumption within a given timeframe. CPIs are commonly employed to index Social Security benefits and pensions. Consumer Price Indexes (CPIs) are widely used to index various payments, serving as a substitute for the overall inflation rate despite their only focus on measuring consumer inflation.

Governments and central banks frequently employ them to establish inflation targets for their monetary policies. Supplementary indices, such as those used to adjust household consumption expenditures in national accounts or the utilization of buying power parities for comparing actual prices, can be derived from the pricing data collected for the Consumer Price Index (CPI) objectives. A worldwide consensus was reached to assign the World Monetary Fund (IMF) and the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) the task of overseeing the global compilation and distribution of national Consumer Price Index (CPI) data. Each country reports the total index of all goods and more particular weights and indexes for the 12 consumer expenditure subcategories, as per the COICOP categorization. The successful implementation of this gateway relies heavily on the ongoing collaboration of all participating nations, as the extensive dataset it provides serves as a vital resource for data consumers worldwide. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) assumes the role of data collection for all nations. At the same time, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has the task of gathering and validating data specifically for its member countries, encompassing accession and key partner nations.

To calculate the annual CPI, the BLS divides the value of a specific basket of goods today compared to one year ago:

$$\text{Annual CPI} = \frac{\text{Value of Basket in Current Year}}{\text{Value of Basket in Prior Year}} \times 100$$

As mentioned earlier, the basket of goods and services used in the CPI calculation is a composite of popular items commonly purchased by Americans. The weight of each component of the basket is in proportion to how they are sold. The annual CPI is reported as a whole number, and the figure is often greater than 100 (assuming current market prices are appreciating).

2.4 Inflation (CPI)

The CPI is an index that measures the relative price change of a basket of products and services that consumers use to meet their wants and requirements. The majority of Consumer Price Index (CPI) calculations include the determination of weighted averages. These averages are derived from the percentage price increases of certain consumer goods baskets. The weights assigned to each item correspond to their relative significance in household consumption during a specified time frame. CPIs are commonly employed to index Social Security benefits and pensions. Consumer Price Indexes (CPIs) are widely used to index various payments, serving as a substitute for the overall inflation rate despite their only focus on measuring consumer inflation.

Governments and central banks frequently employ inflation targets to establish objectives for their monetary policies; other indices, such as price indices, are utilized for adjusting household consumption expenses. Price indices are commonly employed to make adjustments to household consumption expenditures. Price indices are frequently employed to make adjustments to household consumption expenditures. The price indices used to modify household consumption expenditures in national accounts and the buying power parities utilized for comparing actual prices can be constructed using the pricing data gathered for the Consumer Price Index (CPI) objectives.

The international community reached a consensus that the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) would be entrusted with the task of globally collecting and distributing national Consumer Price Index (CPI) data. Each country presents the total index of all goods and the corresponding weights and indexes for the 12 consumer expenditure subcategories based on the COICOP categorization. The successful implementation of this gateway relies heavily on the ongoing collaboration of all participating nations, as the extensive dataset it provides serves as a vital resource for global data consumers. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) is responsible for collecting data from all nations. At the same time, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) focuses on gathering and verifying data specifically for its member countries, which includes accession and significant partner nations.

The inflation rate is calculated by utilising the Consumer Price Index (CPI) of the current year and the CPI of the previous year.

Then, it is used the current year's CPI and the prior year's CPI to calculate the inflation rate.

$$\text{Inflation Rate} = \frac{\text{New CPI} - \text{Prior CPI}}{\text{Prior CPI}} \times 100$$

The inflation rate can be calculated for a given month or annual period; in either case, the appropriate new and prior period must be selected. The inflation rate is reported as a percentage and is often positive (assuming current market prices are appreciating).

2.5 Historical Volatility

Historical volatility indicates a price's propensity to stray from its average over time. As a result, increasing price volatility leads to a higher historical volatility value. The historical volatility number mostly reflects the degree of market instability rather than any specific price trend.

Volatility is commonly employed as a metric to assess the level of risk associated with an investment. The presence of heightened volatility serves as an indicator of amplified levels of risk and uncertainty. Conversely, reduced volatility indicates a decrease in both anticipation and risk. Historical volatility is often employed with various trading patterns, trends, and indicators to ascertain assets that traders see as risky or highly volatile, a common anticipation in financial instrument trading.

Traders who exclusively trade underlying financial assets might use historical volatility as a valuable tool. The measurement of market volatility can impact an investor's expectations of the extent of market fluctuations. Additionally, it can offer guidance in establishing price projections and executing trades.

Aggressive buying or selling in the market can change the prevailing trend since the substantial volume of transactions can lead to observable price reversals. The measurement of a security's price divergence from its typical value can be accomplished through historical volatility (HV). Historical volatility provides a comprehensive outlook on the extent to which traded prices may have deviated from a central or moving average price in marketplaces characterized by a prevailing trend. While the HV value exhibits a consistent pattern of change over time, it does not undergo significant fluctuations daily. The historical and implied volatility is compared to assess the potential under- or overvaluation of options. The Hazard Value (HV) measure is common in evaluating and appraising risks.

2.6 Volatility

The frequency of changes in the price of financial assets over time is measured by volatility. This demonstrates the possible risks connected to a security's price changes. Investors and traders calculate an asset's volatility in order to examine previous price variations and predict future ones.

2.7 Price and Returns

GDP between assets may be difficult to compare. Thus, it is natural to want to think of prices in relative terms. Let P_t denote the price of an asset at time t . Then the return of an asset captures these relative movements and is defined as

$$R_t = \frac{P_t - P_{t-1}}{P_{t-1}}$$

In words, a return is the change in price of an asset, relative to its previous value. Note that $P_t > 0$, and therefore $R_t > -1$. Equation can be rewritten as

$$R_t = \frac{P_t}{P_{t-1}} - 1$$

Methods and Methodology

Myanmar, Singapore, and Thailand are chosen as case studies for this analysis of ASEAN countries. To investigate, data on the secondary annual values of the consumer price index and per capita GDP from 1990 to 2021 were gathered from the World Bank Statistical Organizations and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). The Consumer Price Index (CPI) calculation is based on data from 2010. The per capita gross domestic product (GDP) in the current year, measured in US dollars, is an indicator for assessing economic growth. Descriptive statistics, including measures such as mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and coefficient of variation, are utilized to evaluate and analyze the economic conditions of the three chosen countries. Additionally, an exponential growth curve model is employed for analysis. The dataset encompasses the period from 1990 to 2021.

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

The formula of descriptive statistics on mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, minimum and maximum are as follows:

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

Where

n = number of observations

$\bar{x}$ = mean

x_i = i th value ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$)

Standard deviation $s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{(n-1)}}$

Coefficient of variation: $CV = \frac{s}{\bar{x}} * 100$

3.2 Exponential Growth Curve Model

According to Wooldridge, J. M., (2013), many econometric time series are better approximated by exponential growth curve model, when a series has the same average growth rate from period to period. Exponential growth curve model is

$$Y_t = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 x_t} \varepsilon_t$$

Estimated exponential model $\ln \hat{Y}_t = \ln b_0 + b_1 x_t$

The empirical model use is

$\ln \text{GDP per capita} = \ln b_0 + b_1 \text{CPI}$

Empirical results of consumer price index on economic growth

GDP per capita (current year) is used as a proxy of economic growth to examine the impact of the consumer price index (CPI) on economic growth. The study employs an exponential growth curve model to investigate the influence of the consumer price index (CPI) on economic growth. This model utilises annual time series data from 1990 to 2021, with the CPI as the independent variable. The Consumer Price Index (CPI) for Myanmar, Thailand, and Singapore is computed using 2010 as the reference year.

4.1.1 Impact of Consumer Price Index on Economic Growth of Myanmar

The impact of consumer price index on economic growth of Myanmar is analyzed by using exponential growth curve model. The consumer price index (2010 a base year) is defined as exponent (independent variable) and the economic growth is defined as dependent variable. The analysis results obtained are shown in Figure (4.1).

Figure 4.1 CPI and GDP of Myanmar (1990-2021)

Figure (4.1) shows that Myanmar's GDP per capita followed an inverted U-shaped curve, which indicates a continuous increase from 1990 to 2000. However, from 2001, Myanmar experienced a significant upward trend in per capita GDP growth, surpassing other countries until 2014. In both 2016 and 2021, a decline in per capita GDP was observed. Furthermore, it was observed that Myanmar experienced a significant surge in per capita GDP in the year 2020. In contrast, the consumer price index in Myanmar saw a moderate increase from 2001 to 2021. Even though Myanmar citizens have experienced an increase in their income, there has been a continuous reduction in the purchasing power of their currency from 2001 to 2021.

Table 4.1 Results of Descriptive Statistics for CPI and per capita GDP (current year (US \$)) of Myanmar (1990-2021)

Myanmar	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min	Max	Coefficient of Variation (%)
GDP per capita	557.170	518.787	50.78	1477.45	93.11
CPI	68.101	59.833	1.68	183.51	87.86

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix)

According to the data presented in Table 4.1, the average per capita GDP was 57.170, with a standard deviation of 518.787 and a range value of 1426.67. These values were higher than the average CPI, which was determined to be 68.101, with a standard deviation of 59.833 and a range value of 181.83. The coefficient of variation for GDP per capita was 93.11%, while the coefficient for CPI was 87.86%. The higher average per capita GDP indicates that, during the study period, individual citizens of Myanmar earned incomes that exceeded their expenditures. Nevertheless, the elevated standard deviation, range, and coefficient of variation in per capita GDP indicate that their income levels were unstable, perhaps due to severe inflation during that period.

Table 4.2 illustrates the predicted exponential growth curve model for Myanmar. The Consumer Price Index (CPI) coefficient, specifically 0.019, has statistical significance at a 1% confidence level, as shown by a p-value of less than 0.01.

$$\text{Per capita GDP of Myanmar} = 86.759 e^{(0.019)\text{CPI of Myanmar}}$$

$$\text{Ln (per capita GDP of Myanmar)} = \text{Ln}(86.759) + 0.019(\text{CPI of Myanmar})$$

Table 4.2 Model Summary and Coefficient of Myanmar

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
CPI (Myanmar)	0.019	0.001	0.958	18.215	0.000
(Constant)	86.759	8.067		10.755	0.000
R	0.958				
R Square	0.917				
F (p value)	331.789 (0.000)				

Note: The dependent variable is ln(GDP of Myanmar).

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix)

The computed R-value of 0.958 indicates a strong and directed correlation between the consumer price index and the per capita GDP of Myanmar, according to the results of the model summary Table (4.2). The corrected R2 value of 0.917 indicates that about 91.7% of the entire variation in per capita GDP can be accounted for by the fluctuations observed in the consumer price index. According to the estimated exponential growth curve model, the coefficient of the consumer price index (CPI) is determined to be statistically significant at a 1% level of significance ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, the F value of 331.789 demonstrates statistical significance at a significance level of 1% ($p\text{-value} < 0.01$). Hence, the exponential growth curve model is deemed appropriate and applicable to address this issue. The coefficient of the consumer price index, which is 0.019, indicates that a 1% increase in the consumer price index is associated with an average estimated growth of 1.9% per capita GDP in Myanmar.

Figure 4.2 Trend Analysis Plot of Observed and Exponential Growth Curve of Myanmar

4.1.2 Impact of Consumer Price Index on Economic Growth of Thailand

In this section, the impact of Thailand's CPI on Thailand's GDP per capita (current year, US\$) is analyzed using an exponential curve with the independent variable of the CPI of Thailand between 1990 and 2021. In research, the CPI (2010, a base year) of Thailand is defined as the exponent (independent variable), and the GDP per capita (current year, US \$) of Thailand is defined as the dependent variable. Figure (4.3) shows the analysis results of Thailand's CPI and GDP.

Figure 4.3 CPI and GDP per capita (current year, US \$) values of Thailand (1990-2021)

As stated in Figure (4.2), the inverted U-shaped curve of per capita GDP means that Thailand has instability of individual citizen income during the study period. However, according to the steady consumer price index, their purchasing power of money value has been consistent throughout the year from 1990 to 2021.

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistics of CPI and GDP per capita (current year (US \$)) of Thailand (1990-2021)

Thailand	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min	Max	Coefficient of Variation (%)
GDP per capita	3957.651	1961.400	1545.27	7630.04	49.56
CPI	87.597	20.989	49.76	113.69	23.96

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix)

According to the data in Table 4.3, the mean per capita GDP was 3957.651, with a standard deviation of 1961.4 and a range value of 6084.77. These values were observed to be greater than the mean consumer price index, which was recorded as 87.597. The consumer price index also had a standard deviation of 20.989 and a range value of 63.93. The coefficients of variation for per capita GDP and consumer price index were 49.56% and 23.96%, respectively. As previously observed, it has been determined that Thailand exhibits a higher per capita income for its citizens in comparison to the cost of living. However, due to the higher coefficient value on per capita GDP, the individual experienced unstable wages from 1990 to 2021.

Table 4.4 displays the anticipated model of exponential growth for Thailand. The coefficient of the consumer price index, which is 0.022, has statistical significance at the 1% level, as shown by a p-value of less than 0.01. The exponential curve of Thailand has been estimated.

$$\text{GDP of Thailand} = 494.101 e^{(0.022)\text{CPI of Thailand}}$$

$$\text{Ln}(\text{GDP of Thailand}) = \text{Ln}(494.101) + 0.022(\text{CPI of Thailand})$$

Table 4.4 Model Summary and Coefficient of Thailand

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
CPI (Thailand)	0.022	0.002	0.917	12.632	0.000
(Constant)	494.101	78.635		6.283	0.000
R	0.917				
R Square	0.842				
F (p value)	159.576 (0.000)				

Note: The dependent variable is ln(GDP of Thailand).

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix)

Table (4.4) shows a good correlation between Thailand's per capita GDP value and its consumer price index, as indicated by the computed R 0.917. The R square value of 0.842 suggests that the fluctuations in its consumer price index can account for approximately 84.2% of the entire variance in Thailand's per capita GDP. The estimated exponential growth curve model demonstrates statistical significance at a 1% level, as evidenced by its F value of 331.789 (p-value < 0.01). Hence, the adoption of the exponential growth curve model is deemed appropriate. The coefficient of the consumer price index, which is 0.022 (with a p-value of less than 0.01), demonstrates statistical significance at the 1% level. This indicates that, on average, a 1% increase in the consumer price index in Thailand leads to a corresponding 2.2% increase in the estimated per capita.

Figure 4.4 Trend Analysis Plot of Observed and Exponential Curve of Thailand

4.1.3 Impact of CPI on GDP of Singapore

By using exponential curve, the impact of CPI of Singapore on GDP of Singapore is analyzed with independent variable of CPI of Singapore during between 1990 and 2021. In analyzing, the CPI (2010 a base year) of Singapore is defined as exponent (independent variable) and the GDP of Singapore is defined as dependent variable. The analysis results of CPI and GDP of Singapore are shown in below.

Figure 4.5 CPI and GDP values of Singapore (1990-2021)

According to figure (4.5), GDP per capita (Current year, (US \$)) is inverted U-shaped curve. It means that Singapore is fluctuated production. CPI is steady increase 1990 to 2021 in Singapore.

Table 4.5 Descriptive Statistics of CPI and GDP of Singapore (1990-2021)

Singapore	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min	Max	Coefficient of Variation (%)
GDP per capita	37991.151	18302.991	11861.76	72794.00	48.18
CPI	94.638	14.614	71.82	116.83	15.44

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix)

According to the data presented in Table 4.5, the average per capita GDP was 37991.151, with a standard deviation of 18302.991. The range of values for per capita GDP was from 11861.76 to 72794.00. These values were all greater than the mean value of the consumer price index, which was calculated to be 94.638, with a standard deviation of 14.614 and a range of 71.82 to 116.83. The coefficients of variation for per capita GDP and consumer price index were 48.18% and 15.44%, respectively. As previously observed, it has been determined that Singapore exhibits higher per capita income levels compared to the cost of living. Nevertheless, due to the higher magnitude of the coefficient associated with per capita GDP, individuals' wages have exhibited a lack of stability over the period spanning from 1990 to 2021.

Table 4.6 illustrates the predicted exponential growth curve model for Singapore. The coefficient of the consumer price index, which is 0.022, has statistical significance at a 1% confidence level, as shown by a p-value of less than 0.01. The exponential curve of Singapore has been estimated as follows:

$$\text{GDP of Singapore} = 494.101 e^{(0.022)\text{CPI of Singapore}}$$

$$\ln(\text{GDP of Singapore}) = \ln(494.101) + 0.022(\text{CPI of Singapore})$$

Table 4.6 Model Summary and Coefficient of Singapore

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
CPI (Singapore)	0.034	0.002	0.971	22.340	0.000
(Constant)	1342.299	195.797		6.856	0.000
R	0.971				
R Square	0.943				
F (p value)	499.081 (0.000)				

Note: The dependent variable is ln(GDP of Singapore).

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix)

Model summary results lead to an R-value of 0.971. Therefore, a significant correlation exists between the consumer price index and the GDP value of Singapore. With an R2 value of 0.943, it can be inferred that about 94.3% of the fluctuations observed in Singapore's GDP can be accounted for by the corresponding changes in its CPI value. The exponential curve predicted in this study demonstrates statistical significance at the 1% level, as evidenced by an F value of 499.081 (p-value < 0.01). Hence, this nonlinear model is a suitable fit. The Consumer Price Index (CPI) coefficient in Singapore is 0.034, with a p-value of less than 0.01. This indicates that a 1% increase in the CPI is associated with an average increase of 3.4% in GDP per capita.

Figure 4.6 Trend Analysis Plot of Observed and Exponential Curve of Singapore

Conclusion

We used data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank to analyze the economic output and per capita income of three different ASEAN countries (Thailand, Singapore, and Myanmar) from 1990 to 2021. During the study period, Thailand's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) exhibited a consistent and significant annual increase compared to the GDP growth rates of the other two nations. However, it is worth noting that the GDP of Singapore experienced a low level of development compared to Myanmar's. A significant decline in the GDP of the chosen countries was observed during the period spanning from 1996 to 1998. Subsequently, there is a gradual annual growth shown in the GDP estimates. When the Consumer Price Index (CPI) experiences an increase, it indicates inflation, signifying a simultaneous rise in the cost of living. As the cost of products and services rises, the purchasing power of workers diminishes unless there is a corresponding increase in their income. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) experienced growth concurrent with increased wages. The consumer price index inflation in Myanmar exhibits a significant level of inflation at the beginning of the study period. In contrast, Thailand and Singapore had a very modest level of inflation throughout the study period.

Based on an analysis of historical returns and volatility, it can be observed that Thailand exhibits a higher level of volatility in its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) compared to Singapore and Myanmar. Singapore shows higher levels of consumer price inflation, with greater volatility than Thailand and Myanmar.

Based on the analysis of descriptive statistics, it was observed that the coefficient of variation for GDP per capita exhibited a high degree of variability across all nations under consideration, namely Myanmar, Thailand, and Singapore. However, no significant variation was detected in Thailand and Singapore's Consumer Price Index (CPI). Among these three countries, Singapore has the highest level of pricing stability. The Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS), an autonomous central bank in Singapore, has played a pivotal role in preserving price stability utilizing its monetary policy framework and operational strategies. The Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS) has played a significant role in ensuring and maintaining price stability within the Singaporean economy. The Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS) implemented a managed float exchange rate strategy to guide its monetary policy choices. The exchange rate is the primary policy instrument the Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS) employs to control inflation effectively. The

Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS) operates monetary operations within the foreign currency market to exert control over the exchange rate, with the primary objective of maintaining price stability and mitigating the risks of excessive inflation or deflation. The exchange rate functions as a mechanism for absorbing shocks, facilitating the stabilization of import prices and managing imported inflation. The Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS) diligently examines prevailing economic conditions and promptly modifies its exchange rate policy as necessary to sustain price stability. Singapore has a greater influence on the fluctuation of the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) than Thailand and Myanmar.

The exponential model revealed a non-linear association between the consumer price index (CPI) based on the GDP per capita (measured in current US \$). The analysis indicated that a 1.9% increase in the CPI impacted the GDP per capita in Myanmar. The consumer price index in Thailand's economy has a 2.2% impact on GDP per capita. The consumer price index's effect on Singapore's GDP per capita was 3.4%.

Discussion and Suggestion

Historically, Singapore's strong economic underpinnings, effective monetary policy, and astute budgetary management have all contributed to the nation's low CPI volatility. Singapore has regularly experienced significant gross domestic product (GDP) growth. The observed progress can be attributed to the nation's robust export-driven economy, favorable business climate, and strategic investments in key sectors. Thailand has experienced fluctuations in its Consumer Price Index (CPI), ascribed to factors such as fluctuations in food prices, energy costs, and government policies. The economic trajectory of Thailand has demonstrated variability over time, influenced by several factors such as domestic consumption, export dynamics, political stability, and global financial circumstances. The country has a diverse economy characterized by many industries, such as tourism, manufacturing, and agriculture, which substantially contribute to its Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The data suggests that Myanmar exhibits higher levels of volatility in its Consumer Price Index (CPI) compared to Singapore and Thailand. Various causes have impacted inflationary pressures, encompassing constrained market competition, disruptions in the supply chain, and economic restraints, among others. Several socio-political factors, including conflict and economic sanctions, have impacted the country's price stability. The economic growth of Myanmar has undergone significant transformations due to a range of factors, including transitions in governance, internal conflicts, and monetary policy reforms. The country contains a substantial quantity of natural resources, yet a range of challenges, such as insufficient infrastructure, weak institutions, and limited financial accessibility, have hindered its economic performance. Based on the research findings, it is recommended that Myanmar consider several variables, such as the stabilization of the macroeconomic environment and the enhancement of market competition, to reduce barriers to entry across multiple sectors. This approach is crucial for effectively managing volatility in the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and fostering the development of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The objective is to enhance fairness and responsibility in business operations, streamline regulatory processes, and provide a favourable environment for the advancement and success of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The objective is to augment the capabilities and efficiency of organizations responsible for supervising economic governance, which includes regulatory bodies, financial sector monitoring institutions, and anti-corruption agencies. Enhance economic diversification by allocating assistance to industries exhibiting substantial potential for growth, encompassing, but not limited to, manufacturing, tourism, agriculture, and services. The allocation of resources towards investments in education and skills training programs is of utmost importance to foster the development of a skilled and competent labour force.

Furthermore, incorporating sustainable development principles into economic policies and practices is paramount to guaranteeing long-term sustainability and environmental accountability. The successful execution of these propositions by the Myanmar government requires a thorough and synchronized approach. To effectively manage fluctuations in

the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and facilitate the robust expansion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Myanmar, it is imperative to prioritize stability, cultivate a favourable business environment, allocate resources towards the development of human capital, and implement policies that foster inclusive growth.

Future Research

Analyzing the effects of CPI dynamics on policy (such as inflation targeting monetary policy and fiscal policy) on Myanmar's economic growth is one of the areas that needs more research. Thailand and Singapore are two Southeast Asian countries that possess distinct cultural, economic, and political characteristics. Through evaluating current policies and examining potential enhancements, this study aims to offer valuable insights to policymakers regarding the management of inflation and the promotion of sustainable economic growth. Another study area pertains to the comparative analysis of the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and economic growth patterns among nations in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN).

The primary objective of this study was to examine the historical volatility and returns of Thailand, Singapore, and Myanmar over 31 years. This was accomplished through the application of descriptive statistics. Therefore, it is imperative to analyze the volatility of GDP, specifically concerning consumer price inflation. This can be achieved by employing the GARCH model, which allows for examining the impact of consumer price inflation on yearly GDP.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Abbas Rizvi, S. K., Naqvi, B., Bordes, C., & Mirza, N. (2014). Inflation volatility: an Asian perspective. *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 27(1), 280-303.
- [2] Amaral, A., Dyhoum, T. E., Abdou, H. A., & Aljohani, H. M. (2022). Modeling for the Relationship between Monetary Policy and GDP in the USA Using Statistical Methods. *Mathematics*, 10(21), 4137.
- [3] Aisen, A. and Veiga, F.J. (2006) 'Does political instability lead to higher inflation? A panel data analysis,' *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking* 38: 1379-1389.
- [4] Bleaney, M. and Fielding, D. (2002) 'Exchange rate regimes, inflation and output volatility in developing countries,' *Journal of Development Economics* 68: 233-45.
- [5] Bartak, J., Jabłoński, L., & Jastrzębska, A. (2021). Examining GDP growth and its volatility: an episodic approach. *Entropy*, 23(7), 890.
- [6] Cariolle, J. (1970). Measuring macroeconomic volatility-Applications to export revenue data.
- [7] Cariolle, J. (2012). Measuring macroeconomic volatility: applications to export revenue data, 1970-2005. Ferdi, Policy brief B47, March 2012.
- [8] Cazcarro, I., García-Gusano, D., Iribarren, D., Linares, P., Romero, J. C., Arocena, P., ... & Cadarso, M. Á. (2022). Energy-socio-economic-environmental modelling for the EU energy and post-COVID-19 transitions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 805, 150329.

- [9] Da Silva, S. H., Tabak, B. M., Cajueiro, D. O., & Fazio, D. M. (2017). Economic growth, volatility and their interaction: What's the role of finance?. *Economic Systems*, 41(3), 433-444.
- [10] Dapena, J. P. (2006). Volatility of GDP, macro applications and policy implications of real options for structure of capital Markets. *Documento de Trabajo*, 320.
- [11] Debrun, X., & Kapoor, R. (2010). Fiscal Policy and Macroeconomic Stability: Automatic Stabilizers Work. Always and Everywhere WP/10/111, Washington: International Monetary Fund.
- [12] Dhar, U. (2021). Asian Development Bank (ADB), Asian Development Outlook 2020: What Drives Innovation in Asia?.
- [13] Elder, J. (2004) 'Another perspective on the effects of inflation uncertainty,' *Journal of Money Credit and Banking* 36: 911-28.
- [14] Fang, W., & Miller, S. M. (2009). Modeling the volatility of real GDP growth: The case of Japan revisited. *Japan and the world Economy*, 21(3), 312-324.
- [15] Fasanya, I. O., & Adekoya, O. B. (2017). Modelling inflation rate volatility in Nigeria with structural breaks. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 8(1), 175-193.
- [16] Fatás, A. and Mihov, I. (2005) 'Policy volatility, institutions and economic growth,' CEPR discussion paper 5388.
- [17] Fatás, A., & Mihov, I. (2007). Fiscal discipline, volatility and growth. *Fiscal policy stabilization and growth: Prudence or abstinence*, 43-74.
- [18] Fielding, D. (2008). Inflation volatility and economic development: Evidence from Nigeria.
- [19] Gali, G. and Monacelli, T. (2005) 'Monetary policy and exchange rate volatility in a small open economy,' *Review of Economic Studies* 72: 707-34.
- [20] Grier, R. and Grier, K.B. (2006) 'On the real effects of inflation and inflation uncertainty in Mexico,' *Journal of Development Economics* 80: 478-500.
- [21] Gruen, D. W. (1995). Financial market volatility and the world-wide fall in inflation. Reserve Bank of Australia, Economic Research Department.
- [22] Hahn, F. R. (2003). Financial development and macroeconomic volatility. Evidence from OECD Countries (No. 198). WIFO Working Papers.
- [23] Hall, J., & Jääskelä, J. P. (2011). Inflation volatility and forecast accuracy. *Australian Economic Review*, 44(4), 404-417.
- [24] Kasidi, F., & Mwakanemela, K. (2013). Impact of inflation on economic growth: A case study of Tanzania. *Asian Journal of empirical research*, 3(4), 363-380.
- [25] Khan, S. A. R., Ibrahim, R. L., Al-Amin, A. Q., & Yu, Z. (2022). An ideology of sustainability under technological revolution: striving towards sustainable development. *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4415.
- [26] Kuncoro, H. (2014). Does the credible fiscal policy reduce its volatility? The case of Indonesia. *Journal of Applied Economic Sciences (JAES)*, 9(29), 382-393.
- [27] Leduc, S. and Sill, K. (2007) 'Monetary policy, oil shocks, and TFP: Accounting for the decline in US volatility,' *Review of Economic Dynamics* 10: 595-614.
- [28] Lumbay, M., Vigonte, F., & Abante, M. V. (2023). Important Key Drivers, Policies and Socioeconomic Goals to Sustain and Accelerate the Philippine Economy Following the COVID-19 Outbreak. *Policies and Socioeconomic Goals to Sustain and Accelerate the Philippine Economy Following the COVID-19 Outbreak* (February 9, 2023).
- [29] Muhammad, S. A. L. I. M. O. V. (2020). The impact of inflation targeting on inflation volatility (Doctoral dissertation, Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University).
- [30] Nguyen, T. N. A., Pham, T. H. H., & Vallée, T. (2020). Trade volatility in the association of Southeast Asian nations plus three: impacts and determinants. *Asian Development Review*, 37(2), 167-200.

[31] Perry, G. (2003). Can fiscal rules help reduce macroeconomic volatility in the Latin America and Caribbean region? (Vol. 3080). World Bank Publications.

[32] Rother, P. (2004). Fiscal policy and inflation volatility. Available at SSRN 515081.

[33] Saleem, N. (2008). Measuring volatility of inflation in Pakistan. Lahore Journal of Economics, 13(2), 99-128.

[34] Tsatsaronis, K., Chui, M., Goel, T., & Mehrotra, A. (2022). The monetary-fiscal policy nexus in the wake of the pandemic. BIS Papers Chapters, 122, 1-25.

[35] Wooldridge, J. M., (2013) Introductory Econometrics, A Modern Approach Nafziger, E. W., Economic Development 4th edition,

[36] <https://data.oecd.org/price/inflation-cpi.htm>

[37] <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG>

[38] <https://www.google.com/search?q=IMF+Data+Consumer+Price+Inflation>

[39] <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fandd/issues/Series/Back-to-Basics/gross-domestic-product-GDP>

[40] <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/what-is-gdp-why-its-important-to-economists-investors/>

[41] https://www.aseanstats.org/wpcontent/uploads/2019/11/ASEAN_Stats_Leaflet_2019.pdf

¹ Tin Zar Zar Lynn
 School of Economics
 Guangxi University School of Economics, Nanning, 530004, China